
Landscape Analysis Report

The Environment in
Which IReL Operates

April 2026

Ireland's
higher education
and research
landscape

National policy
and
infrastructure

International
developments

IReL
today

Research
Consulting

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Background and scope of work

This document provides factual context on the national and international environment in which the **Irish Research eLibrary (IREL)** operates, to support the stakeholder engagement process and inform the development of IREL's first strategic plan. It is intended as a reference document and a starting point for discussion.

Ireland's higher education and research landscape

The Irish higher education landscape

Ireland's higher education sector comprises eight Irish University Association (IUA) universities, **five technological universities (TUs)** represented by the Technological Universities Association (TUA), two institutes of technology and a range of other publicly funded research-performing organisations. **IREL's 18 member institutions** span this full spectrum, meaning its strategic plan needs to resonate across organisations with very different research profiles and expectations of a national shared service.

Research and development expenditure

Ireland's total R&D spending grew by approximately 77% over the decade since 2012, and government budget allocations for R&D (GBARD) have increased by over 28% over the same period, surpassing €1 billion for the first time in 2023.

Gross Expenditure on R&D (GERD) across all sectors was estimated at €4.9 billion, with the business sector accounting for over 80% of the total. The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) notes that **Ireland's overall R&D expenditure fell by 2.4% in real terms** in 2023 following a major boost in 2022 driven by large multinational capital projects, illustrating the volatility a small number of investments can introduce. **R&D expenditure in the higher education sector was €854 million in 2022**, a 15.1% increase on the previous (2020) survey, representing approximately 18% of total GERD. These figures reflect where research is *performed* rather than who funds it.

Because Ireland's headline Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is inflated by multinational activity, standard international comparisons of R&D intensity can be misleading. The OECD average R&D intensity stands at 2.7% of GDP and the EU27 average at 2.1%. **Ireland's total R&D intensity on a GDP basis is approximately 1.5%**, placing it well below both benchmarks. **Impact 2030**, the government's current research and innovation strategy, signals a commitment to sustained investment but does not set an explicit R&D intensity target.

Figure 1: Gross domestic expenditure on R&D as a percentage of GDP (source: OECD)

Irish scholarly output

Figure 2 shows trends in Irish research output from 2007 to 2025, drawing on data from the **National OA Monitor**. Total publications from Irish-affiliated authors grew steadily until 2022, roughly tripling from approximately 12,500 in 2007 to a peak of around 36,500 in

2022. The sharp increase between 2019 and 2022 partly reflects the global surge in publication volumes due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Since then, output has returned to pre-pandemic levels. Peer-reviewed publications followed a similar trajectory. The volume of open access peer-reviewed publications grew steadily from under 3,000 in 2007 to a peak of approximately 19,000 in 2020, and has also declined since. The gap between total peer-reviewed output and licensed OA output has plateaued in recent years. Note that 2025 figures may be affected by incomplete data coverage given their recency.

Figure 2: Ireland’s publication trend (source: National Open Access Monitor Ireland)

National policy and infrastructure

Impact 2030: Ireland’s research and innovation strategy

Impact 2030, the whole-of-government research and innovation strategy, was launched in May 2022. It is built on five pillars and contains 30 flagship initiatives, with its second pillar specifically committing to open research and research integrity. By July 2023, 29 of 30 flagship initiatives were reported as delivered or well-progressed. One of the most significant outcomes of Impact 2030 has been the creation of Research Ireland (Taighde Éireann), established through the Research and Innovation Act 2024, merging Science Foundation Ireland and the Irish Research Council into a single funder with a statutory duty to support research across all disciplines. Its strategy was launched on 2 March 2026, organised around three themes: Talent, Economy, and Society.

Research Ireland’s Interim Open Research Policy

Science Foundation Ireland and the Irish Research Council were both members of cOAlition S (an initiative to make full and immediate open access to research publications a reality). Research Ireland’s Interim Open Research Policy (effective April 2025) requires immediate open access from the date of publication, with mandatory repository deposit. CC BY licensing is required. Article processing charges (APCs) may be paid from grants for fully OA journals but are not permitted for hybrid journals. The policy also requires data access statements, persistent identifiers (DOI, ORCID), and encourages rights retention statements and open peer review. The policy states that Research Ireland will monitor compliance "through various means and on an ongoing basis", with grant recipients required to report on their publications’ OA status as part of standard reporting.

INSPIRE: a generational infrastructure investment

The INSPIRE Programme provides €750 million over five years for research infrastructure, with €100 million in the first year. It is administered jointly by the Higher Education Authority and Research Ireland. The programme defines two categories: local institutional infrastructure (€25,000–€500,000) and shared advanced infrastructures (>€500,000). Phase One opened in Q1 2026.

INSPIRE is primarily focused on physical research equipment rather than digital scholarly infrastructure directly. However, the INSPIRE working group report explicitly identified

IRel as an exemplar infrastructure, and there may be scope to align any infrastructure requirements emerging from the strategic plan with INSPIRE funding opportunities.

NORF and the National Action Plan for Open Research

The [National Open Research Forum \(NORF\)](#), established in 2017, is managed by the [Digital Repository of Ireland](#) and co-chaired by the [Higher Education Authority](#) and the [Health Research Board](#). Its flagship output is the [National Action Plan for Open Research 2022-2030](#), targeting 100% open access to publicly funded research publications by 2030. The target also includes books but acknowledges that embargo periods may be permitted but "should be as short as possible". The plan supports multiple routes to OA (including Green and Gold) without embargo for journal articles and is subject to periodic review every three years.

NORF has invested approximately €4 million across three Open Research Fund rounds, supporting projects including the [National OA Monitor](#) (led by IRel), [PublishOA](#) (a feasibility study for a national Diamond OA publishing platform, co-led by the Royal Irish Academy and Trinity College Dublin), [TROPIC](#) (TRaining in Open Research in an Irish Context), the data stewardship network [Sonraí](#), and [Open Repositories Ireland](#). The PublishOA project [published a landscape report](#) on scholarly publishing in Ireland in June 2025, mapping Irish publishers and assessing Diamond OA readiness. Briefly, the landscape report identified 212 publishers on the island of Ireland, the vast majority operating as micro-enterprises, and found that Diamond OA publishing remains largely confined to university department journals. Neither of Ireland's two main humanities university presses has yet published open access, citing concerns about financial sustainability and the risk of losing authors to larger UK-based presses. The report concluded that a mixed model of Green, Gold and Diamond OA, rather than a purely Diamond approach, is likely to be the most realistic route toward the national 100% OA target.

[NORF's 2025 Open Research Fund Call](#) specifically targeted the sustainability of these established initiatives, signalling a shift from project-based to ongoing infrastructure.

Other key NORF outputs include the [National Persistent Identifier \(PID\) Strategy and Roadmap](#) which identified four priority PIDs: Digital Object Identifiers (DOI), Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID), Research Activity Identifiers (RAiD), Research Organisation Registry (ROR) and estimated that a central PID support service would yield over 4,000 days of staff time savings per year (approximately €1.8 million) across 25 Irish institutions. An [Irish Chapter of CoARA](#) (the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment) was approved in 2023, and the [Irish Reproducibility Network](#) launched in January 2026.

International Developments

This section summarises the international developments most relevant to IRel's strategic environment. The focus is selective: IRel's centrally funded model is unusual, shared by very few peers internationally. Norway's former Unit consortium (now [SIKT](#)) and, to some extent, Finland's [FinELib](#) and the [Netherlands' UKB](#) operate with varying degrees of central coordination, but none replicate Ireland's fully national funding model.

European Research Area and EOSC

The second [European Research Area \(ERA\) Policy Agenda \(2025-2027\)](#) includes Structural Policy 1, committing to developing the [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#) federation and increasing FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) research data, and ERA Action 1, which targets support for high-quality not-for-profit OA scholarly publishing. A major development under ERA Action 1 is [Open Research Europe \(ORE\)](#),

originally launched by the European Commission in 2021 as a free open access publishing platform for Horizon-funded researchers. ORE is now being transformed into a collective non-profit publishing service, with CERN approved as the hosting organisation in December 2025 and national funders from Austria, France, Germany, Norway, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain, and Sweden signing on to co-fund the platform from 2026. This will allow all researchers in those countries to publish on ORE at no cost, regardless of funding source. Ireland is not currently among the participating funders. Ireland's EOSC connection **currently runs through HEAnet**; whether there is a role for library or publishing infrastructure in that engagement is an open question.

UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science

The **UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science** (2021), adopted by 194 Member States, provides the global normative framework. The first monitoring cycle required national reports by March 2025, with 77 countries reporting. Ireland's OA Monitor was submitted as a best-practice case study. The next reporting cycle (~2029) falls within IRel's strategic plan period.

Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information

The **Barcelona Declaration** calls for openness of research metadata and reduced dependence on proprietary analytics systems. Launched with approximately 40 initial signatories, it has since grown to around 134 signatories including universities, funders, and library consortia across Europe. There are currently no Irish signatories. IRel's negotiation principles explicitly require publishers to support open access monitoring through the use of appropriate metadata, and the OA Monitor (built with **OpenAIRE**, a Declaration supporter) is closely aligned with the Declaration's goals. IRel has also been asked to consider negotiating a national deal for Scopus, but has not pursued this on the grounds that proprietary analytics products do not align with its open-infrastructure direction, a position the Barcelona Declaration reinforces.

Open access publishing: a shifting landscape

The **cOAlition S Strategy 2026-2030** marks a significant shift. The coalition now endorses multiple routes to OA (diamond OA, preprints, the Publish-Review-Curate model) and ceased financial support for transformative agreements from 31 December 2024. Diamond OA is identified as a major pillar, with an estimated 17,000-29,000 diamond journals operating worldwide.

The **ESAC Registry** surpassed 1,000 transformative agreements in April 2024, spanning 70+ countries. Questions are emerging about **the long-term sustainability of TAs** and whether they entrench rather than transform the current publishing model. For example, Sweden's Bidsam Consortium has announced **it should not sign agreements for reading and publishing in hybrid journals from 2026**.

These international questions have direct relevance for Ireland. Achieving 100% open access through current publishing-agreement approaches would likely carry significant costs. Transformative agreements typically bundle reading access and open access publishing into a single negotiation. Growing research output translates into growing costs for transformative agreements, as publishers use rising publication volumes to justify higher fees, even though the value of the reading component diminishes.

IRel's existing agreements cover the major international publishers. Extending the same approach to the many smaller publishers in the remaining portion of the portfolio could be disproportionately resource-intensive relative to the OA output gained. Alternative approaches, including pure publish agreements or **Subscribe to Open**, may offer more practical routes for these parts of the portfolio though this depends more on the publishers rather than IRel.

AI and research integrity Major publishers are launching AI-powered research platforms ([Wiley AI Gateway](#), [Elsevier's LeapSpace](#)) that represent entirely new product categories. If researchers come to depend on these tools, then they could become part of future negotiations, adding a new dimension to what consortia like IReL are expected to secure access to. Research integrity has also become a growing concern, with over [10,000 articles retracted globally in 2023](#) alone and [publishers investing significantly in detecting and preventing integrity breaches](#). These costs are ultimately reflected in what publishers charge for their services, adding to the cost pressures consortia like IReL face.

Research assessment reform The [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#) has grown to over 800 signatories from 55+ countries, with an Irish chapter approved in 2023. The [San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment \(DORA\)](#), which recognises the need to improve how researchers and their outputs are evaluated, has over 25,000 signatories. Ireland's participation in these initiatives connects to IReL's work through the publication data IReL manages and the metadata infrastructure that underpins responsible research assessment. This positions IReL at the intersection of publishing data and assessment reform. This connection may become more significant as Irish institutions respond to CoARA commitments and national policy signals around responsible metrics.

The Association of European Research Libraries (LIBER) [LIBER's 2023-2027](#) strategy for its 420+ member research libraries (including 11 Irish libraries) prioritises open science, FAIR data, responsible research assessment, and workforce development. IReL has active LIBER engagement, for example, [Susan Reilly presenting at the 2025 Annual Conference on the National OA Monitor](#).

Calls for publishing reform A number of recent reports and events have converged around a shared conclusion: that the scholarly publishing system requires fundamental reform. A [Cambridge University Press report](#) identified four interlocking challenges — publishing volume, financial sustainability, equality gaps, and the rewarding of quantity over quality — and called for radical collective action at institutional, national, and global levels. The OASPA position paper '[From Percentage to Participation](#)', drawing on 107 stakeholders across 26 countries, reached similar conclusions, highlighting inequity in publishing models, limited sustainable funding, and geographic and economic barriers to participation. [The Stockholm Declaration](#), published in Royal Society Open Science following a workshop at the Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences, focused on the growing threat of paper mills and AI-generated fraudulent publications, calling on academia to resume control of publishing through non-profit models and to reform incentive systems that reward quantity over quality. Separately, the growing use of generative AI tools is enabling researchers to produce manuscripts more quickly, contributing to sustained growth in submission and publication volumes across the sector.

An arXiv paper, '[The Drain of Scientific Publishing](#)', argued that the concentration of publishing among major commercial publishers in the Global North is harmful to science and called for collective action to re-communalise publishing. These themes were echoed at a [workshop in Pisa](#) co-hosted by ASAPbio, CWTS, DORA, and the ISC, which emphasised discipline-specific approaches and community governance as routes to reform. Alongside these calls, the Open Journal Collective has launched a [global investment campaign](#) offering libraries a single mechanism to support 284 DOAJ-indexed diamond OA journals across AHSS and STEM, providing a community-led alternative to commercial publishing models.

All of these developments are happening during a period of sustained and accelerating growth in global publication volumes. [Figure 3](#), drawing on Dimensions data, shows that

total global published articles have more than tripled since 2004, from approximately 1.8 million to over 6.5 million per year. Open access publications have also grown substantially, rising from around a quarter of output to approximately two-thirds by 2023. In recent years the gap between total and OA publications has widened in absolute terms. [Analysis by James Butcher](#) suggests that the global OA transition has stalled and may even be reversing, driven in large part by the rapid growth in research output from China, where researchers predominantly publish in subscription journals and few transformative agreements are in place. For IReL, this has direct practical implications: transformative agreements face growing cost pressure from rising publication volumes, while the proportion of global output that remains behind paywalls is proving more resistant to change than earlier trends suggested.

Figure 3: Global article volumes and OA share (source: Dimensions)

IReL today

IReL was established in 2004 by university librarians to negotiate shared access to journals and research databases on behalf of Irish institutions. IReL initially focused on science, technology and medicine resources, and later expanded to include the humanities and social sciences. Hosted by Maynooth University, IReL is a nationally funded shared service, a unique model with few internationally comparable arrangements. Today, [IReL serves 18 member institutions](#) and manages over [20 active OA publishing agreements](#) covering more than 10,000 journals. Ireland ranks among the leading countries globally for open access and is the global leader in [the ESAC Market Watch](#) for the proportion of OA publishing enabled through transformative agreements.

IReL's mission

IReL's [mission](#) is "to provide sustainable and inclusive access to scholarly communications in support of Irish research excellence and impact." It achieves this through four pillars:

1. providing shared access to published information
2. supporting authors to publish openly
3. partnering locally and globally to develop an open and diverse scholarly communications ecosystem
4. responsible use of public funding

IReL's work is guided by five values: openness, equity, integrity, sustainability, and collaboration.

Negotiation principles

IReL's [negotiation principles](#) commit to cost reduction and control, uncapped open access at no author-facing charge, full transparency (no non-disclosure clauses), concrete publisher commitment to OA transition, and equity in global pricing. These principles have

been enforced. For example, the [ACS agreement reverted to read-only in 2026](#) where pricing and terms for open access were unsatisfactory.

Strategic review of IReL (2019)

In 2019, a Steering Group chaired by the Higher Education Authority conducted [an independent strategic review of IReL](#), comprising a value-for-money assessment by Mazars and an options review by BH Associates. The review confirmed that IReL delivered value for money and set out recommendations across six areas:

- national procurement (continue and expand consortium purchasing)
- membership (expand on a phased basis to IoTs/TUs and other publicly funded RPOs)
- funding model (reform toward FTE-based cost-sharing with tiered access)
- governance (move to a competence-based board model with a dedicated negotiations committee)
- staff training (increase professional development, particularly in negotiation)
- IReL's future role and remit (explore a wider national procurement function for all electronic research publications)

The review also flagged areas for national-level consideration: comprehensive data collection on national e-resource spending, the role of repositories in meeting the open access challenge, and adoption of the DORA principles for research assessment.

IReL has made significant progress against these recommendations. Membership has expanded from the traditional universities to include all five technological universities, two remaining institutes of technology, and specialist bodies. A full-time director was appointed. The team has grown to 9 staff. A mission statement and negotiation principles have been published. Open access publishing agreements have expanded to over 20 publishers, and IReL has taken on new national roles including the OA Monitor, the ORCID and DataCite consortia, and open repositories coordination. The question now is how to build on this progress in a more considered and strategic way, which is the purpose of this first strategic plan.

The National Open Access Monitor

The National Open Access Monitor, launched March 2024 with OpenAIRE, tracks over 500,000 publications and has been submitted to UNESCO as a best-practice case study. Ireland's monitor is among only a handful of nationally-coordinated OA tracking systems worldwide.

IReL also leads the Irish ORCID and DataCite consortia, coordinates with Open Repositories Ireland (launched December 2024).

IReL and its role in relation to eBooks

While books fall within IReL's remit, dedicated eBook procurement has not been a strategic priority to date. The NORF Action Plan includes books within its 100% OA target (with embargo periods permitted), and the PublishOA landscape report highlights the challenges Irish university presses face in transitioning to OA. Whether books should become a more active part of IReL's work over the next strategy period is an open question.

Questions to be explored in the strategic planning process

The following questions are drawn from this landscape analysis to help frame discussion during the development of IRel's strategic plan. They are intended as prompts, not as predetermined strategic directions.

On OA publishing and the evolving TA model:

IRel's transformative agreements have been highly effective, but the international landscape is shifting. How should IRel's approach to publisher agreements evolve over the next five years? What role should alternative publishing models (diamond OA, Subscribe to Open) and green OA play alongside or instead of current approaches?

On IRel's role beyond access to reading and publishing:

IRel now operates the OA Monitor, leads the ORCID and DataCite consortia, and coordinates with Open Repositories Ireland. How far should IRel's remit extend beyond e-resource licensing? Are there areas (e.g. PID coordination, metadata quality, eBooks, or support for research data infrastructure) where members see IRel playing a stronger role?

On national policy alignment:

Research Ireland's new Open Research Policy, the NORF Action Plan's 100% OA target, and the INSPIRE infrastructure programme all create opportunities for alignment. How can IRel's strategy complement these national initiatives, and where should it lead rather than follow?

On membership and governance:

The 2019 review recommended further membership expansion. IRel's membership now spans institutions with very different research profiles. How can the strategic plan ensure that priorities resonate across research-intensive universities, technological universities, and specialist bodies?

On international engagement:

IRel's negotiation principles and the OA Monitor align with the goals of the Barcelona Declaration, and there are opportunities to deepen engagement with ERA/EOSC, LIBER, and CoARA. Which international relationships and frameworks should IRel prioritise?

On emerging challenges:

Publisher AI products, research integrity concerns, and the growing importance of AI/TDM clauses in licensing agreements are reshaping the content landscape. How should IRel prepare for these developments?